

Gender and merit in awarding cum laude for the PhD thesis

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Abstract

In the Dutch academic system, PhD theses can be awarded with 'Cum Laude', and only some 5% of all PhD graduates receive this selective award. In this paper, we investigate whether there is gender bias in awarding cum laude, using data from a major Dutch research university. We measure the quality of the PhD thesis using bibliometric data. A main result is that the set of PhD theses receiving cum laude do on average not have a higher quality than the best theses not getting cum laude. A second main result is that, after controlling for the quality of the PhD thesis, women have a substantially lower probability to be granted cum laude. These results strongly suggest that the distribution of awards may contribute to gender bias. These findings lead to a strong doubt about the adequacy of the procedures leading to awarding cum laude for the PhD thesis.

Introduction

Within the Netherlands higher education system, awarding a PhD thesis with the qualification 'cum laude' (with honors; abbreviated as CL) does not happen often. It may differ between universities and faculties, but the overall 4.3% of our case seems a good estimate. It has been shown that men are awarded *cum laude* for their PhD thesis more frequently than women are, and this seems to be the case in all Dutch universities (De Bruin 2018). This is not unimportant, as cum laude awards are of considerable help in the early academic career (Brouns et al. 2004). This may even have increased in the more recent period (Reschke et al. 2018).

In this report we try to answer the question is whether this observed gender difference is a form of gender bias. Is the difference between men and women because the peer reviewers adequately pick out the best dissertations and that there happen to be more male than female authors among those? Or is the decision biased, and in this case especially gender biased, and what mechanisms might cause such bias? As gender differences in *cum laude* do not fit with the generally accepted policies within Dutch higher education to promote gender equality, an explanation for the existing disparities is needed.

We analyze data for one of the Dutch universities in order to contribute to the understanding of this phenomenon. Is the gender difference in *cum laude* an effect of gender bias, or do peer and panel reviews correctly reflect the quality differences of the dissertations?

There are hardly studies available on gender bias in cum laude awards. But there are studies on other types of awards and prizes, all suggesting the existence of gender bias (Lincoln et al. 2012; Melnikoff & Valian 2019; Silver et al. 2018). Furthermore, men also receive other signs of prestige more than women do, such as invitations for keynote speaker at scientific conferences (Casadevall & Handelsman 2014; Dumitra et al. 2019; Johnson et al. 2016; Klein et al. 2017; Sardelis & Drew 2016), for other invited talks (Nittrouer et al. 2017), or invitations for e.g., scientific advisory boards (Ding et al. 2020?)

Apart from that, the general peer review literature has shown the many uncertainties and biases in peer and panel review processes (Chubin & Hackett 1990; Cole et al. 1977, 1982; Cole 1991;

Lamont 2010; Van Arensbergen et al. 2014), making it unlikely that the committee-based evaluation of PhD theses would be completely unbiased.

Gender differences versus gender bias

If there are strong gender differences in getting cum laude for the PhD thesis, the question is whether we have to classify those differences as gender bias. Bias implies a deviation of what would be correct and merit-based decisions (Merton 1973). Therefore, the selection of a frame of reference for measuring merit is crucial. One perspective is *distributional equality*, and that would imply that the share of female PhD students that receive a cum laude should be equal to the share of male PhD students that get cum laude. Here we use a widely accepted view that science is a *merit-based system* and that implies that cum laude awards should go to the best PhD students with the best doctoral dissertations. Bias can be defined as deviation from this norm.

This of course does not immediately solve the problem, as one may have different opinions how to decide what are the best dissertations and who are the best PhD students. E.g., should the most talented PhD students or the best performing ones receive the cum laude award? And how does one objectively measure who are the best PhD students or what are the best theses? We suggest that cum laude is meant as a recognition of the quality of the thesis itself, and we assume that the higher the quality, the more highly cited papers result from the thesis. Of course, this does not work in an absolute way, and one would not expect correlation of 1 between the quality of the thesis and the number of highly cited papers coming out of the thesis work. However, one would expect that the *set of cum laude theses* would have higher *average* bibliometric scores than a set of very good, but not cum laude awarded dissertations.

If we measure the quality of the PhD research by measuring the impact of the related output, the question can be answered whether the observed *gender differences* in receiving cum laude are a form of *gender bias*. In an earlier study, we showed that there are persisting differences between men and women researchers in terms of output and impact, and relevant for this study, these gender differences appear to occur specifically in the top of the performance distribution (Fig 1): Among the group of high productive and high impact researchers, male researchers are strongly overrepresented (Van den Besselaar & Sandström 2017).

**Figure 1: Share of men (Y-axis) by productivity level (X-axis: full counts)
(Note that the number of researchers declines fast with the increase of productivity)**

The figure shows only publication-counts, but elsewhere we showed that high numbers of publications lead to high numbers of highly cited papers (Sandström & Van den Besselaar 2016). This finding may be relevant for the current study, as the cum laude recipients are expected to belong to that top segment. This means that the fact that women less often receive cum laude may not be bias, but the effect male researchers being over-represented in the top-performers segment. We will test that in this paper.

The case

The case is a large research-intensive university in the Netherlands, in the top 100 in the Leiden Ranking (2019) – based on the share of top 10% cited papers¹. We cover in this study the period between 2000 and 2018. In that period, 5732 doctorates were awarded by the university, with a substantial annual growth: In 2000 it where 177 doctorates, increasing to 433 in 2018. The share of female PhDs increased from 39.5% in 2000 to 52.0% in 2018, with an average of 48%. In that period, 248 theses were granted cum laude, of which about 34% to women. As table 1 shows, men have almost twice as high a probability to receive cum laude.

Table 1. Cum laude by gender*

	Male	Female	Total	F/M
Cum laude	165	83	248	0.50
No cum laude	2834	2646	5481	0.93
Total	2999	2729	5728	0.91
Share cum laude (%)	5.5	3.0	4.3	0.55

* Source: Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, 2000-2018, 1 case has missing gender

If we distinguish between disciplines, quite some differences become visible. First of all, the numbers of PhDs per discipline differ strongly in this case. Some 36% of all PhD degrees are from medicine plus 2% from dentistry, and 28% from the two science faculties. The remaining 34% are divided among the other disciplines, with behavioral and movement sciences (with a share of about 10%) as largest of the smaller fields. Table 2 gives the details.

Table 2. Faculty by cum laude (2000 - 2018)

faculty	# PhDs	Share of		Faculty share
		PhDs	# CL	
Theology and Religious Studies	236	4.1%	21	8.9%
Social Sciences	291	5.1%	22	7.6%
Humanities	317	5.5%	25	7.9%
Law	169	2.9%	14	8.3%
Natural Sciences	888	15.5%	38	4.3%
Earth and life Sciences	717	12.5%	14	2.0%
Behavioral & movement sciences	559	9.8%	36	6.4%
Business and Economics	383	6.7%	6	1.6%
Dentistry	109	1.9%	3	2.8%
Medicine	2060	36.0%	69	3.3%
Total	5729		248	

This set of 5729 PhD students were supervised by in total 3988 supervisors in different roles. Most of them (88.4%) were never involved in awarding cum laude, as one already would expect from the small number of CL awardees (Table 3). Table 3 shows that the actual cum laude chance of a PhD student in group of ‘cum laude giving supervisors’ is 8.4% (248 out of 2733).

¹ The university has 14.1% of its publications within the top 10% category.

7. P10%FN	Number of papers in the set of 10% highest cited papers, field normalized
8. PP10%	Share of top 10% cited papers in the oeuvre
9. PP10%FN	Share of top 10% cited papers in the oeuvre, field normalized
10. P10%frac	Number of papers in the set of 10 % highest cited papers, fractionally counted
11. PP10%FNfrac	Share of top 10% cited papers cited papers, field normalized, fractionally counted
12. Average FWCI	Average field weighted citation impact
13. Sum FWCI	Sum field weighted citation impact
14. SNIP	Source (journal) normalized impact per paper
15. SJR	SCimago Journal Rank ('impact factor')

Publication behavior and citation behavior differ between fields, and therefore the indicators are often field normalized. And as most papers are co-authored, and co-author behavior also differs between fields, many indicators correct for the number of co-authors ('fractional counting'). The indicators measure different aspects of quality and do so in different ways. For example, P, Pfrac, P10%, and P10%frac each measure some aspect of *productivity*. P simply measures full output, Pfrac corrects for the number of authors, P10% only takes the top cited papers into account, and P10%frac does this while correcting for the number of co-authors. The last two indicators also measure *impact*, as is also done by other citation-based indicators. Finally, some indicators do not measure the impact of the work of the authors, but the impact of the journals the papers are published in. These indicators are probably measuring reputation, more than impact or quality.

A next issue is the period covered by the measurement. The obvious period to take into account are the years of the PhD trajectory and a few years after the moment of awarding the PhD. But the committee may also have assessed the *potential* of the researchers, and may have based the cum laude decision also on *expected (future) excellence*. This can be measured by the performance indicators over a longer period after the dissertation was finished.

As we measure the quality of the thesis using citation-based indicators, we restrict the analysis to the period 2000-2014. The more recent years cannot be included, as we lack a sufficient long period for measuring the citations: the bibliometric data were collected in late 2019. Overall, this leads to a set of (only) 120 cum laude dissertations out of 3306 dissertations – 3,6%.

We only include in our analysis those research fields for which journal articles are the main research output. This excludes from this study most of the social sciences, the humanities, law and theology. Fortunately, those are also the fields with a lower gender difference in awarding cum laude (Table 7). Psychology and economics are included, as in those fields journal articles are dominant. Consequently, we include all dissertations in the *sciences*, *mathematics* and *computer science*, in the *earth and life sciences*, in the *medical sciences* and *dentistry*, in *economics* and in *psychology* and *movement sciences*. Due to the large number of medical dissertations, we decided to include all the medical cum laude dissertations and 50% of the dissertations that did not receive cum laude.³

Data

The names and other information about PhD students (such as gender and whether they were granted cum laude) was provided by the university. For 2592 researchers from our sample of 3306 we collected the publication and citation data using Scopus (summer 2019), which then

³ We use a stratified sample that represents the distribution over years and over gender in the total set. Within each category, the 50% was selected randomly. The very labor-intensive part of the study was the collection of performance data from (in this case) Scopus.

were controlled and cleaned, and then used to retrieve the mentioned indicators covering the selected periods.

For selecting the supervisors, we followed the following approach.

- We made a list of all first, second and third supervisors, and first, second and third co-supervisors. From that we made a list of unique supervisors.
- For all supervisors with 3 and more PhD students the bibliometric data were collected.
- Then we checked whether we had for all PhD students at least one supervisor with bibliometric data. For those we hadn't, we selected one of the other supervisors of that PhD student and collected the bibliometric data also for these supervisors. In this way we succeeded to find for almost every PhD student bibliometric data for at least one of his/her supervisors. Where we had these indicators for more than one of the supervisors, we used the one with the highest performance in the statistical analyses.

As table 6 shows, we collected and cleaned for 3306 researchers their bibliometric data, which was a very time-consuming activity.

Table 6. Available bibliometric data

	PhD students	Supervisors
Collected bibliometric data (Scopus)	2592	812
No bibliometric data	714*	3176

* All of these are in medicine.

Methods

As publication, collaboration and citation behavior differs between the disciplines, we first *standardize* the performance indicators *by faculty* and in such a way that the mean of the performance indicators is 0 and the standard deviation is 1.

As explained in the previous section, the bibliometric indicators all measure in some way quality, and therefore we consider the various indicators *as items*, together measuring various underlying dimensions of the construct *quality*. A principal component analysis (oblique rotation; component scores saved with regression) resulted in three dimensions, together explaining almost 80% of the variance.⁴ The resulting variables represent three distinct quality dimensions⁵:

- Dimension 1: *Relative impact* of the oeuvre of a researcher: *share* of top cited papers in the total oeuvre of the researcher, the average FWCI, and citations per publication:
- Dimension 2: *Total impact (and output)* of the researcher, in fractional count, consisting of the following indicators:⁶
- Dimension 3: *Journal impact*:

The *total impact* dimension includes the indicators measuring total output, total impact, and the sum of highly cited papers, suggesting that higher quantity produces also a higher quantity of top papers (Sandström & Van den Besselaar 2016). We tested whether the indicators also form reliable scales, and that is the case. The Cronbach Alpha for the three indicators are 0.911 (5 items), 0.861 (3 items), and 0.851 (2 items) respectively, and cannot be improved by leaving out one of the items⁷. Concluding, we have a quality concept with the three mentioned dimensions (total, relative, and journal impact) and the scales used to measure those are reliable.

⁴ The principal component analyses were done on both the whole career data and the PhD period data.

⁵ The items belonging to each component are explained above.

⁶ We do not use the full-count based indicators, but when including those, they load together with the fractional-count based publication and citation indicators (here component 2).

⁷ For the career data the Cronbach Alpha's are .911 .929 and .849 for component 1,2 and 3 respectively.

The data are analyzed using logistic regression (the dependent variable is binary: cum laude or no cum laude). The logistic regression is first done for men and women separately, in order to test whether the independent performance variables have a similar effect for women or not. If not, we have to include interaction terms between gender and the performance variables in the analysis.

Then we run a logistic regression also including gender as a variable. The odds ratio for gender gives a first insight in the effect of gender (bias) on getting cum laude. However, the odds ratio only gives the value of the dependent variable for the independent variables at value = 0. As logistic regression is non-linear, the gender differences may be dependent on the level of the independent (here: performance) variables (Mood 2009). In order to correct for this, we calculate the predicted probabilities (using the predicted margins in STATA) to display the probability to receive cum laude by gender for a variety of values of the performance variables. After having done this, we did a few controls, that is we restrict the sample of PhD receivers to those with at least one supervisor that has at least one PhD student with cum laude, and run the same analyses – this because only a small subgroup of supervisors has supervised a PhD student that was awarded cum laude. By restricting the analysis to this set of supervisors, we may get a better picture of what variables affect the probability to get cum laude. Secondly, we restrict the sample to the cum laude awardees plus the best performing non-cum laude PhD receivers, to assess whether CL was indeed awarded to the best PhD students.

Findings

Who receives the CL-award? Some basic findings.

As reported above, overall about 4.3% of the PhD recipients were awarded cum laude, and men twice as often as women. Did this change over time? In Figure 2, we show a breakdown over the period 2000-2018. The figure shows for each year the share of female PhD students that received cum laude divided by the share of male PhD students who received cum laude, as well as the opposite: male divided by female. In 2001, only men (14 in total) received cum laude, and no women. Given these strong fluctuations, we show in Figure 2 the raw data, as well as a 5-years moving average.

Figure 2. Cum laude by gender over time

The linear regression line suggests convergence, but this is mainly due to the extreme 2001 score – when deleting that year, no change is visible on the longer run. This makes our study easier: we can take the whole period as one data set – which is an advantage as the cum laude numbers are rather low.

Table 7 gives a break down by field, showing that the *stronger codified fields* (the STEM fields, and the mathematics-oriented fields like economics) have a low percentage of PhD theses with cum laude (between 1.6% and 3.3%). In these fields, the probability that men receive cum laude is twice as high (or more) as for women.

Within social sciences, law, and religion studies, the share of PhD students receiving cum laude is substantially higher (between 7.6% and 8.9%), and the differences between men and women are relatively small. Psychology and humanities have an ambiguous position. Psychology – which often presents itself as a STEM related field - belongs to that group when we look at the gender differences. However, behavioral (psychology) and movement sciences have a much higher percentage of PhD students that receive cum laude. These are more similar to the other social sciences. The same holds for the humanities: with respect to the share of PhDs with cum laude, humanities are similar to the social sciences, but in terms of gender differences it belongs to the group with the STEM fields and economics (and psychology).

Table 7. Cum laude by gender and faculty (2000 - 2018)

Faculty	share	M-Total	W-Total	% CL	M-CL	W-CL	M-CL%	W-CL%	W/M
Earth and life Sciences	12.5%	379	338	2.0%	9	5	2.4%	1.5%	0.62
Natural Sciences	15.5%	645	243	4.3%	33	5	5.1%	2.1%	0.40
Dentistry	1.9%	56	53	2.8%	2	1	3.6%	1.9%	0.53
Medicine	36.0%	849	1211	3.3%	40	29	4.7%	2.4%	0.51
Business and Economics	6.7%	277	105	1.6%	6	0	2.2%	0.0%	0.00
Behavioral & movement sciences	9.8%	221	338	6.4%	21	15	9.5%	4.4%	0.47
Humanities	5.5%	174	143	7.9%	18	7	10.3%	4.9%	0.47
Social Sciences	5.1%	123	168	7.6%	11	11	8.9%	6.5%	0.73
Law	3.0%	81	88	8.3%	7	7	8.6%	8.0%	0.92
Theology and Religious Studies	4.1%	194	42	8.9%	18	3	9.3%	7.1%	0.77

M-total: total number male PhDs; W-total: total number female PhDs; %CL: percentage of PhDs with Cum Laude; M-CL: met with cum laude; F-CL: women with cum laude; M-CL%: percentage men with com laude; F-CL%: percentage women with cum laude; W/M = W-CL%/M-CL%

Who awards cum laude: Basic findings

Not all supervisors have supervised a PhD student that received cum laude; in fact, most of the supervisors (88.4 %) have not as Table 8a shows. Of all students that had at least one supervisor that had at least once awarded cum laude, the share of female PhD students is 48.9%, and of all PhD students that had only supervisors who were never involved in awarding cum laude, the share of female PhD students is 46.29% (Table 8b). Therefore, the low share of women among cum laude awardees is not a distributional effect: that would only be so if those supervisors that award cum laude would have a very low number of female PhD students – which is not the case.

Table 8a. Who awards cum laude?

	# sup	% sup	# CL	# PhD	% CL
has awarded cum laude	462	11.60%	248	2981	8.3%
has not awarded cum laude	3526	88.40%	0	4884	0.0%

* Source: Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, 2000-2018, 1 case has missing gender. Note that there are non cum laude PhDs who have supervisors from both groups, as a consequence the bottom number of PhDs contains some of the same PhDs as the top number.

Table 8b. Who receives cum laude?

	# PhD	%		# CL	% CL	# F		
		PhDs	PhDs			PhD	MPhD	PhD
PhDs with CL granting supervisor	2981	52.0%		248	8.3%	1457	1523	48.9%
PhDs without CL granting supervisor	2748	48.0%		0	0	1272	1476	46.3%

* Source: Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, 2000-2018, 1 case has missing gender

Furthermore, those supervisors that did award cum laude, do that in various frequencies. Some have high percentages cum laude receivers as, whereas others have lower percentages – but we found that those supervisors who do award a cum laude, do that on average for about 8.3 of his/her PhD students – much higher than the overall average. Of course, when you have only one or two PhD students, and one of them gets a cum laude, the percentages are 100% and 50%, but also quite a few of the supervisors with many PhD student have a high share of cum laude receivers. The other way around, there are also supervisors with many PhD students that never awarded cum laude. This leads to the following question: Do those supervisors that never awarded cum laude have lower quality PhD students, or do they have other reasons for this? We will address this issue later in the report.

Summarizing, awarding CL is very unevenly distributed among supervisors, and the different success rates for male and female PhD students is not explained by the gender distribution of the PhD students among those two groups of supervisors.

Gender bias?

We started with a logistic regression for men and women separately, and test whether the independent performance variables have the same effect on the probability to get cum laude for men and women. This is the case, and we therefore do not need to include interaction terms in the analysis. In order to test whether women have less chance to be awarded cum laude, we use a logistic regression with *yes/no Cum Laude* as dependent variable. As independent variables, we use the three impact variables and gender, and we add as control variables the faculty and the year of receiving the PhD. Table 9 shows the results. Two impact variables (absolute and journal impact) have a significant *positive* effect on the probability of obtaining cum laude, and the relative impact has *no effect*. Being *female* has a negative effect on the probability to get cum laude: the odds ratio for gender is 0.49 suggesting that men get twice as often CL than women after controlling for performance.

Table 9. Cum laude by gender, faculty and quality*

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Sex of PhD candidate(1)	-0.714	0.228	9.824	1	0.002	0.49	0.313	0.765
faculty			33.673	5	0			
faculty(1)	-0.702	0.258	7.373	1	0.007	0.496	0.299	0.823
faculty(2)	-1.806	0.402	20.154	1	0	0.164	0.075	0.362
faculty(3)	0.004	0.268	0	1	0.988	1.004	0.594	1.697
faculty(4)	-1.677	0.495	11.462	1	0.001	0.187	0.071	0.494
faculty(5)	-1.125	0.764	2.164	1	0.141	0.325	0.073	1.453
PhD year	-0.041	0.024	2.967	1	0.085	0.96	0.916	1.006
relative impact (PhD period)	0.02	0.1	0.042	1	0.838	1.021	0.839	1.241
total impact (PhD period)	0.465	0.066	49.777	1	0	1.592	1.399	1.812
journal impact (PhD period)	0.474	0.093	26.051	1	0	1.606	1.339	1.926
Constant	-2.143	0.265	65.64	1	0	0.117		

* Logistic regression; all PhD students in the selected faculties; ** Indicators calculated over the t-3 ~ t+3 period; N=2579; Nagelkerke R Square: 0.177

The odds ratio for gender reported above is sensitive for non-linearity, and only measures the gender effect for independent variables = 0. Therefore, we calculate the predicted probability to receive cum laude for men and women *at the various levels of the independent variables*. This is done using STATA, and the results are in Figure 3a-3d.

For each level of the *relative impact*, men have a higher probability to get cum laude than women do, although the performance variable itself makes no difference. For the *absolute impact/output* and for the *journal impact*, the analysis shows that at the lower levels of the independent variables there is no gender difference, but the higher the performance level, the larger the distance between men and women. One would expect that CL awardees are at the higher level of performance, so gender does play a role. At these high-performance levels, the 95% confidence intervals start to overlap, which is due to the low number of observations at those levels. These predictive margins support the gender difference found in the logistic regression. The last figure 3d shows that over the years, the probability to get cum laude declines, but the men-women ratio remains about constant: In each year men get it about twice as often as women do – even after controlling for performance.

Figures 3a-3d: Predictive margins of probability to receive cum laude by sex

Cum laude recipients versus the best non-recipients

As we controlled for the three quality variables, the result suggests that there should be enough high performing women that would – based on their performance – qualify for cum laude. Therefore, it is useful to have a closer look into the set of researchers with high high-quality dissertations. That group is defined in the following way. We select for each of the disciplines and for the two quality dimensions (*total impact/output* and *journal impact*)⁸ the best scoring non-cum laude researchers. The threshold is chosen in such way that we include about 10% of all researchers in a field in the ‘top sample’. Then we aggregate these two ‘top samples’ with the CL-recipients into one sample consisting of 519 researchers. However, there one case with a bibliometric data error, resulting a final set of 518.

We then deploy the same logistic regression for this smaller top group. Within the top group, the relative impact variable has no significant effect, but the two other quality variables (absolute impact and journal impact) have a negative effect: within the top, higher performance results in a lower probability to get cum laude – suggesting a flawed selection process (table 10).

Within the top group, being female lowers the probability to get CL considerably: the odds ratio is 0.582, not much different from the result of the previous analysis. The predictive margins show again that with a similar score on the independent variables, men have a higher probability than women to be awarded cum laude.

⁸ We exclude the relative impact, as that variable did not have any effect on getting cum laude (see table 9)

Table 10. Cum laude by gender, faculty and quality*

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Sex of PhD candidate	-0.542	0.258	4.41	1	0.036	0.582	0.351	0.965
faculty			38.106	5	0			
faculty(1)	0.418	0.296	1.989	1	0.158	1.519	0.85	2.714
faculty(2)	-1.056	0.411	6.611	1	0.01	0.348	0.156	0.778
faculty(3)	1.553	0.357	18.945	1	0	4.726	2.348	9.51
faculty(4)	-0.876	0.513	2.918	1	0.088	0.416	0.152	1.138
faculty(5)	-0.481	0.812	0.351	1	0.553	0.618	0.126	3.035
PhD year minus 1999	-0.007	0.027	0.06	1	0.807	0.993	0.941	1.048
PhD period relative output	-0.124	0.113	1.191	1	0.275	0.884	0.708	1.103
PhD period total impact and output	-0.150	0.081	3.417	1	0.065	0.861	0.734	1.009
PhD period journal impact	-0.364	0.113	10.37	1	0.001	0.695	0.557	0.867
Constant	-0.538	0.308	3.056	1	0.08	0.584		

* Logistic regression; all PhD students in the top segment; ** Indicators calculated over the t-3 ~ t+3 period; N=518; Nagelkerke R Square: 0.173

Figures 4a-4d: Predictive margins of probability to receive cum laude by sex, 3 factor top group.

Conclusions

The raw data showed that men get twice as often cum laude than women do. In the logistic regression, we controlled for quality of the PhD thesis, for the faculty of the PhD student, and (where needed) for the year of obtaining the PhD degree. We find that gender has again a strong and for women negative effect on the probability to receive CL. In fact, the control variables do hardly change the strong effect of gender on the probability to receive a CL award.

Secondly, when comparing the predicted probabilities to get a cum laude, we find that for the low performing men and women the probability is equally low, but the higher the performance level the larger the gender difference: the highest performing women overall have a much lower probability to get cum laude than men do.

Thirdly, we find that cum laude PhDs do not outperform the best performing PhDs who did not get cum laude. On the contrary, the cum laude receivers are in some impact indicators outperformed by the best performing non-cum laude PhDs – especially those that were supervised with non-cum laude supervisors. This indicates that some of the best PhD students may not have received CL because awarding CL was not an option for their supervisors.

Fourthly, the data show that several of the CL-recipients have a very low (Scopus covered) output and impact – in the PhD period but also over the career until 2018. In the fields under study here, this is rather remarkable.

As cum laude may have strong career effects, our result suggest that the current procedure may create unjustified differences.

Limitations

This study has a few limitations that should be mentioned. Firstly, one may dispute the way the quality of the PhD theses is measured using bibliometric indicators. However, as no other independent assessments of the theses exist, this is the best option for the moment. We also would defend the approach: an excellent PhD thesis can be expected to lead (in the fields we covered here) to impactful papers. And although a lot of randomness may affect the citations received at the individual level, at the group level one would expect that CL-dissertations would lead to higher scores on the impact variables we deploy than the non-CL-dissertations. A second issue that should be mentioned is the selection of the top groups: Our top includes about 24% of the total population. One may find this too high, and it would be reasonable to use a more selective definition. However, if we would make the top group smaller, then the difference with the cum laude receivers will even increase, as the more restricted group of non-CL top performers will have even higher impact scores. Then the cum laude receivers will clearly underperform compared to the others in the top. Thirdly, the explained variance (Nagelkerke pseudo R^2) found in the various regression analyses are rather low, suggesting that other factors than gender and impact may be behind the cum laude decision.

Further work

This last issue leads to further work. We would expect that three factors not included in this report may partly explain the cum laude decision: (1) the personal relation between the supervisor(s) and the PhD student, (2) the personality of the PhD student, and (3) differences between the supervisors.

As supervisors have to select who they would like propose for cum laude, the quality of the personal relations between the PhD student and the supervisor may be important. We are currently analyzing that using the acknowledgement texts that are included in most of the PhD theses. Can we derive from those text indicators for the personal relation between the supervisor and the PhD student? One would expect as language is an expression of relationships, opinions and emotions (Pennebaker et al. 2001; Tausik & Pennebaker 2010).

Another factor is the personality of the PhD student: can we distinguish cum laude receivers from others in terms of personal characteristics? In order to test this, we have distributed a questionnaire to measure personality dimensions of the PhD students, and the analysis we are doing now should give a first indication whether the CL award may be more awarding the person(ality) than the quality and impact of the science. By the way both variables (social relation with the supervisor and personality) may have a gender dimension.

Finally, some characteristics of the supervisors may play a role, such as the scientific quality and the attitude towards the cum laude award. Also these we intend to add in a follow-up paper.

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